

The State of Circularity in the Ibero-American Countries and the Role of FabLabs and Makerspaces. Exploring Circular Innovation: Insights from the First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting

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1 Introduction

As the global community grapples with escalating environmental crises and the urgent need for sustainable development, the role of innovation and collaboration becomes paramount. This paper explores the evolving landscape of circularity in the Ibero-American countries through the lens of FabLabs and makerspaces, which are, little by little, at the forefront of fostering sustainable practices across the region. With an emphasis on Spanish and Portuguese-speaking countries belonging to the Ibero-American region, this study delves into the integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and circular economy principles within these innovative hubs.

The Ibero-American region formed by the following countries: Spain, Portugal, Chile, Uruguay, Puerto Rico, Argentina, Brazil, Dominican Republic, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, El Salvador, Paraguay, Nicaragua, Guatemala, Bolivia, Venezuela and Cuba, presents a unique blend of cultural diversity and developmental challenges. This paper investigates how FabLabs and makerspaces in these countries are not only advancing technological and educational frontiers but also they are starting to contribute significantly to circular economy initiatives. These efforts are crucial for transforming traditional linear consumption and production models into sustainable, regenerative systems that enhance the well-being of both people and the planet.

This comprehensive analysis aims to highlight the transformative potential of FabLabs and makerspaces in promoting circularity. By examining their contributions and what they can do in the fields of education, production, industry, and biodiversity, the paper underscores the pivotal role these entities play in driving the region towards a more sustainable and equitable future. Through this exploration, we

seek to provide insights into the strategies that can amplify their impact and foster a deeper understanding of circular economy practices within the Ibero-American context.

2 Sustainable Development Goals

2.1 Definition

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or Global Goals, were established by the United Nations in 2015 as a universal call to action to eliminate poverty, protect the planet, and ensure peace and prosperity for all by 2030. Comprising 17 interconnected goals, the SDGs acknowledge that progress in one area impacts others, necessitating a balance between social, economic, and environmental sustainability.

Countries are committed to prioritizing progress for the most marginalized populations. According to UNDP (United Nations development Programm) the SDGs aim to eradicate poverty, hunger, AIDS, and gender discrimination. Achieving these goals requires the collective creativity, expertise, technology, and financial resources from all sectors of society in every context.

The SDGs and their goals see the SDG website at <https://sdgs.un.org/>.

2.2 Sustainable Development Report 2024: SDGs in Ibero-American Region

The Sustainable Development Report 2024, produced by independent experts at the SDG Transformation Center, offers the latest data to evaluate and rank global progress towards the SDGs. This year's report highlights five key findings, noting that only 16% of SDG targets are on track globally to be met by 2030, with significant disparities in progress among different countries. The report underscores the urgent need for financial reforms, global cooperation, and innovative solutions to address food and land system challenges.

Figure 1. Relationship between SDGs ranking, level and trends of Ibero-American countries. Derived from accompanying data (Sachs, J. et al. 2024)

Ibero-American Region faces significant and major challenges across most SDGs, with many countries showing stagnation or moderate progress in their trends.

For a more detailed level and trends information of Ibero-American countries see Annex 2.

2.3 Summary of levels and trends in Ibero-American Region

In line with the Report, the Ibero-American region faces widespread and significant challenges across most SDGs, with many countries showing stagnation or only moderate progress. Efforts to reduce poverty, hunger, and inequality are particularly lagging, while some improvements are noted in health, education, and clean energy. The findings underscore the urgent need for more effective policies and initiatives to drive sustainable development and achieve the SDGs by 2030.

SDG 1 - No Poverty

The region shows significant challenges with poverty reduction, where 10 countries face significant challenges and 1 country faces major challenges. Trends indicate stagnation in 10 countries, suggesting that efforts to alleviate poverty are not progressing sufficiently.

SDG 2 - Zero Hunger

Hunger remains a critical issue, with 15 countries experiencing major challenges. Most countries (16) are stagnating in their progress, indicating little to no improvement in food security.

SDG 3 - Good Health and Well-being

Health and well-being present significant challenges for 10 countries and major challenges for 9. However, 14 countries show moderate increases in health outcomes, indicating some progress but with substantial room for improvement.

SDG 4 - Quality Education

Education quality is problematic, with significant challenges in 12 countries and major challenges in 2. Trends show stagnation in 11 countries and moderate increases in 7, highlighting a need for more effective educational reforms.

SDG 5 - Gender Equality

Gender equality faces significant challenges in 10 countries. Trends are more positive, with 14 countries showing moderate increases and 4 on track, suggesting gradual progress in addressing gender disparities.

SDG 6 - Clean Water and Sanitation

Access to clean water and sanitation is a significant challenge for 12 countries, with major challenges in 6. The trend is moderately increasing in 15 countries, indicating some improvement in water and sanitation infrastructure.

SDG 7 - Affordable and Clean Energy

Energy access shows significant challenges in 9 countries. Trends are moderately increasing in 16 countries, reflecting gradual progress in improving energy access and sustainability.

SDG 8 - Decent Work and Economic Growth

Economic growth and employment face significant challenges in 11 countries, with major challenges in 6. Stagnation is observed in 10 countries, suggesting that economic policies are not sufficiently driving growth and employment.

SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

Industrial and infrastructural development is hampered by significant challenges in 11 countries and major challenges in 10. Trends show moderate increases in 13 countries, indicating some progress but with substantial hurdles remaining.

SDG 10 - Reduced Inequalities

Inequality is a major challenge for 16 countries. Trends show stagnation in 9 countries, highlighting the difficulty in achieving equitable growth and social inclusion.

SDG 11 - Sustainable Cities and Communities

Urban sustainability faces significant challenges in 9 countries and major challenges in 8. Stagnation in 10 countries indicates slow progress in making cities more sustainable and resilient.

SDG 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production

Sustainable consumption and production are significant challenges for 7 countries, with major challenges in 6. Trends show stagnation in 11 countries, reflecting slow adoption of sustainable practices.

SDG 13 - Climate Action

Climate action faces significant challenges in 2 countries and major challenges in 5. Trends are more positive, with 7 countries on track, suggesting some successful climate initiatives but overall slow progress.

SDG 14 - Life Below Water

Marine conservation is a major challenge for 14 countries. Trends show stagnation in 15 countries, indicating limited progress in protecting marine ecosystems.

SDG 15 - Life on Land

Terrestrial ecosystems face major challenges in 17 countries. Stagnation in 19 countries suggests that conservation efforts are insufficient to halt biodiversity loss and land degradation.

SDG 16 - Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions

Governance and institutional strength are major challenges in 17 countries. Trends show stagnation in 17 countries, reflecting persistent issues in establishing effective, transparent, and accountable institutions.

SDG 17 - Partnerships for the Goals

Collaboration for sustainable development faces significant challenges in 13 countries. Trends are moderately increasing in 11 countries, indicating some progress in fostering partnerships but highlighting the need for stronger international cooperation.

3 Circular Economy

3.1 Definition

The literature review reveals that there is no universally accepted or straightforward definition for Circular economy (CE). For this paper we follow the definition given by Ellen McArthur Foundation in their website:

“The circular economy is a system where materials never become waste and nature is regenerated. In a circular economy, products and materials are kept in circulation through processes like maintenance, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, recycling, and composting. The circular economy tackles climate change and other global challenges, like biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution, by decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources.

The circular economy is based on three principles, driven by design:

- *Eliminate waste and pollution*
- *Circulate products and materials (at their highest value)*
- *Regenerate nature*

Underpinned by a transition to renewable energy and materials, the circular economy is a resilient system that is good for business, people, and the environment.”

3.2 The Circularity Gap Report 2024: CE in Ibero-American Region

The Circularity Gap Report 2024 asks the question “how can we ensure people’s wellbeing while operating within our planet’s boundaries across air, land and water?” This question represents the ultimate challenge of 21st century: while material consumption has significantly improved living standards—boosting life expectancy, employment, and education—it also increases ecological impact. Rising Human Development Index (HDI) correlates with greater environmental damage. Material consumption accounts for 70% of global greenhouse gas emissions and drives over 90% of biodiversity loss and water stress.

Figure 2. Illustrates the relationship between countries' Human Development Index (HDI) and their Material Footprint. As HDI increases, environmental impacts also rise.

Source: the Circularity Gap Report 2024, p. 18.

To tackle the challenge the Circularity Gap Report 2024 proposes 12 solutions related with 4 key global systems (vital for fulfilling people’s needs: nutrition, built environment, manufactured goods and transport & mobility that put the most pressure on 7 planetary boundary overshoots: climate change, ocean acidification, nitrogen cycle, phosphorus emissions, atmospheric aerosol loading, freshwater use and land use. These solutions are:

1. Food system:

- Put healthier, satiating foods first.
- Mainstream regenerative agricultura.
- Go local seasonal and organic.
- End avoidable food waste.

2. Built environment:

- - Make the most of what already exists.
- - Utilise secondary materials.
- - Be as energy efficient as posible.
- - Prioritise circular materials and approaches.

3. Manufactured goods:

- - Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency.
- - Buy what’s needed.
- - Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods.
- - Eschew fast fashion in favor of sustainable textiles.

Figure 3. Shows the relation between global vital systems, planetary boundary overshoots, country profiles and circular proposed solutions. Source: Source is Fraser et al. (2024), p. 25.

The Report have used the country profiles Build, Grow and Shift (first developed in the Circularity Gap Report 2020) to select the most relevant two key systems and two circular solutions for countries to focus on:

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Figure 4. Country profiles (Shift and Grow) corresponding to Ibero-American region.

To ensure global wellbeing within planetary limits, we need to focus on circular development in lower-income Build countries, encourage circular industrial processes in Grow countries, and change consumption habits in higher-income Shift nations.

Ibero - American region is marked in the profiles Shift Countries (Spain, Portugal and Argentina) and Build Countries (Chile, Uruguay, Puerto Rico, Brazil, Dominican Republic, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, El Salvador, Paraguay, Nicaragua, Guatemala, Bolivia, Venezuela, Cuba). Taking this in account, the Report recommend the next most impactful circular solutions:

1. Food system:
 - Mainstream regenerative agricultura.
 - Go local seasonal and organic.
4. Built environment:
 - Make the most of what already exists.
 - Prioritise circular materials and approaches.
5. Manufactured goods:
 - Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency.
 - Buy what's needed.
 - Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods.

4 Relation between SDGs and CE

After reviewing different sources of literature, we can conclude that SDGs are centered in improving the lives of populations around the world and mitigating the hazardous man-made effects of climate change taking in account sustainable practices. The SDGs goals and targets don't talk about circularity, they just talk about sustainability. Below are the targets related to sustainability.

5 Adoption of SDGs Profiles by Ibero-Americas Fab Labs

5.1 Introduction

The integration of SDGs within Fab Labs is crucial for promoting sustainable practices and fostering innovation aligned with global development targets. In Ibero-America Fab Labs are increasingly adopting SDG profiles to contribute to eliminate poverty, protect the planet, and ensure peace and prosperity for all by 2030.

5.2 Overview of FabLabs with SDG profiles and Fab city Network members: Data Analysis

For the purposes of this article we work with the data provided by Pieter van der Hijden, member of the Working Group Fablabs & SDGs. Through the Interactive Mind Map "Overview of Fab Labs with SDG Profiles and Fab City Network Members" (<https://bit.ly/fablist-sdgs>) we have updated information regarding the adoption of the SDG profiles by the FabLabs country by country.

The countries that have been taken into account for the analysis are the following: Spain, Portugal, Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, El Salvador, Paraguay, Guatemala, Venezuela. The countries that do not appear is because either there are no Fab Labs in the country or, if there are Fab Labs, they have not yet adopted the SDG profile.

5.3 Conclusions

The data on the adoption of SDGs by Ibero-American FabLabs reveals a strong alignment with five key SDGs: Quality Education (SDG 4 - 83,6%), Gender Equality (SDG 5 - 40,8%), Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9 - 69,13), Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11 - 47,46), and Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12 - 35).

6 Matching SDGs, CE and FabLabs

6.1 Methodology

For this article we propose an approach based in words to relate the SDGs, the CE and the Fab Labs of the Ibero-American region through their SDG Profiles. This methodology is divided into 3 steps whose overlap produces the selection of the most relevant SDGs for circular practices taking into account the interests and work of the FabLabs in the field of the SDGs (see Table 3). In the last step, a reflection is made on the SDGs obtained in relation to the recommendations on circular practices made by The Circular Gap Report 2024 of the Circle Economy Foundation.

Step 1:

List of SDGs that contains words from Ellen McArthur Foundation CE definition. These SDGs are: 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 17. It is noteworthy that the following SDGs do not appear in this list:

5-Gender Equality

10-Reduced inequalities

16-Peace, justice and strong institutions

Step 2:

Selection of the SDGs that contains words from Ellen McArthur Foundation CE definition in 4 or more targets. In this case, the SDGs list is: 7, 9, 11, 12, 13 and 15.

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Figure 5. Ibero-American SDG Profiles. WG Fablabs & SDGs.

Spain: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Spain: fablabs: 93; fablab sdg profiles: N = 27 (= 29 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Brazil: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Brazil: fablabs: 173; fablab sdg profiles: N = 54 (= 31 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Portugal: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Portugal: fablabs: 26; fablab sdg profiles: N = 11 (= 42 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Costa Rica: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Costa Rica: fablabs: 11; fablab sdg profiles: N = 3 (= 27 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Chile: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Chile: fablabs: 22; fablab sdg profiles: N = 5 (= 23 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Honduras: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Honduras: fablabs: 2; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 50 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Argentina: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Argentina: fablabs: 20; fablab sdg profiles: N = 5 (= 25 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Peru: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Peru: fablabs: 46; fablab sdg profiles: N = 12 (= 26 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Figure 5. Continued. Ibero-American SDG Profiles.

Colombia: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Colombia: fablabs: 22; fablab sdg profiles: N = 4 (= 18 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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El Salvador: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

El Salvador: fablabs: 6; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 17 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Ecuador: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Ecuador: fablabs: 14; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 7 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Paraguay: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Paraguay: fablabs: 5; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 20 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Mexico: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Mexico: fablabs: 50; fablab sdg profiles: N = 18 (= 36 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
 CC-BY 2024 - Global Working Group Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Guatemala: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Guatemala: fablabs: 7; fablab sdg profiles: N = 3 (= 43 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Panama: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Panama: fablabs: 8; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 12 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
 CC-BY 2024 - Global Working Group Fablabs and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Venezuela: Fablab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies [%]

Venezuela: fablabs: 3; fablab sdg profiles: N = 1 (= 33 %); retrieved: 2024-07-01
 Note: A Fablab SDG Profile is a Fablab's preferred selection of 2-4 SDGs (out of 17)
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Step 3:

We select the predominant SDGs in Ibero-American FabLab SDG Profiles from Table 3. In this occasion the list is: 4, 5, 9, 11 and 12.

Result:

These three steps produce in Table 5 a vertical overlap that throws the common SDGs that connect CE and the predominant SDGs taken into account in the Ibero-American FabLab Network (IberoFABLaT Network)).

The final SDGs list that connects CE with Ibero-American FabLabs Profiles is:

- 9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure
- 11-Sustainable cities and communities
- 12-Responsible consumption and production

Step 4:

At this point the result requires a reflection relating the country profile and the circular practices proposed by the report, and the work of the Fab Labs in relation to the SDGs. The report proposes four vital global systems, three country profiles, two of which represent Ibero-American countries, and for each of them, it proposes several priority circular practices to be implemented in the short term.

- Shift Country Profile:

Housing a quarter of the global population, consume 34% of raw materials. Their material footprint per capita is 4.6 times that of Build countries and 1.6 times that of Grow countries due to high consumption of imported goods.

Circular practices recommended and systems affected:

1. Buy what you need / Manufactured goods.
2. Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods / Manufactured goods.
3. Make the most of what already exists / Built environment.
4. Prioritize circular materials and approaches / Built environment.

Countries: Spain, Portugal, Argentina.

- Grow Country Profile.

Grow countries account for 55% of global raw material extraction and 52% of the material footprint while housing 37% of the world's population.

Circular practices recommended and systems affected:

1. Mainstream regenerative agriculture / Food system.
2. Go local. Seasonal and organic / Food system.
3. Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods / Manufactured goods.
4. Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency / Manufactured goods.

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Figure 6. SDGs targets that contain any word of the definition of CE of Ellen Mc Arthur Foundation. Result of textual analysis by authors of: United Nations (2015) and Ellen Mc Arthur Foundation

Table 5. SDGs that connect CE with Ibero-American FabLabs Profiles.

Item	1 - No poverty	2 - Zero hunger	3 - Good health and well being	4 - Quality education	5 - Gender Equality	6 - Clean water and sanitation	7 - Affordable and clean energy	8 - Decent work and economic grow	9 - Industry, innovation and infrastructure	10 - Reduced inequalities	11 - Sustainable cities and communities	12 - Responsible consumption and production	13 - Climate action	14 - Life below water	15 - Life on land	16 - Peace, justice and strong institutions	17 - Partnerships for the goals
STEP 1 / SDGs that contains words from the Ellen McArthur Foundation CE definition.																	
STEP 2 / SDGs that contains words from the Ellen McArthur Foundation CE definition in 4 or more targets.																	
STEP 3 / Predominant SDGs in Ibero-American FabLab SDG Profiles																	

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Countries: Chile, Uruguay, Puerto Rico, Brazil, Dominican Republic, Costa Rica, Honduras, Peru, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, El Salvador, Paraguay, Nicaragua, Guatemala, Bolivia, Venezuela, Cuba.

Table 6 lists the country profile, the circular practices recommended by the report and the SDGs relevant to the CE within the Ibero-American fabLabs.

Table 6. Relation between SDGs, circular practices, country profiles and key vital systems.

	MANUFACTURED GOODS			BUILT ENVIRONMENT			FOOD SYSTEM		
	9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure	11-Sustainable cities and communities	12-Responsible consumption and production	9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure	11-Sustainable cities and communities	12-Responsible consumption and production	9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure	11-Sustainable cities and communities	12-Responsible consumption and production
Shift Country Profile	Circular practice 1	Buy what you need	Buy what you need	Buy what you need					
	Relation with SDG	9.1, 9.4, 9.a, 9.b	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5					
	Circular practice 2				Make the most of what already exists	Make the most of what already exists	Make the most of what already exists		
	Relation with SDG				9.1, 9.4, 9.a, 9.b	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5		
	Circular practice 3	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods					
	Relation with SDG	9.1, 9.4	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5					
	Circular practice 4				Prioritize circular materials and approaches	Prioritize circular materials and approaches	Prioritize circular materials and approaches		
	Relation with SDG				9.1, 9.4	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5		
Grow Country Profile	Circular practice 1						Mainstream regenerative agriculture	Mainstream regenerative agriculture	Mainstream regenerative agriculture
	Relation with SDG						9.4	11.6, 11.b	12.4, 12.5
	Circular practice 2						Go local. Seasonal and organic	Go local. Seasonal and organic	Go local. Seasonal and organic
	Relation with SDG						11.6, 11.b	11.6, 11.b	12.4, 12.5
	Circular practice 3	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods	Extend the lifetime of machinery, equipment and goods					
	Relation with SDG	9.1, 9.4	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5					
	Circular practice 4	Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency	Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency	Mainstream industrial symbiosis and efficiency					
	Relation with SDG	9.1, 9.4	11.6, 11.b	12.3, 12.4, 12.5					

6.2 Findings and results

Fab Labs, with their focus on innovation and digital manufacturing, can significantly contribute to circular practices by integrating and promoting SDGs, particularly SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). Here are some key ways Fab Labs can facilitate these practices:

1. Resource Efficiency and Sustainable Consumption

Circular Practice: Buy What You Need

Fab Labs can educate communities on the importance of purchasing only necessary items, thereby reducing waste and promoting sustainable consumption.

Relation to SDGs: This practice aligns with SDG 9.1, 9.4, 9.a, 9.b, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.3, 12.4, 12.5.

Circular Practice: Make the Most of What Already Exists

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Encouraging the use of existing resources and materials, Fab Labs can foster a culture of reuse and repurposing, extending the lifecycle of products and reducing the need for new raw materials.

Relation to SDGs: Supports SDG 9.1, 9.4, 9.a, 9.b, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.3, 12.4, 12.5.

2. Extending the Lifespan of Products

Circular Practice: Extend the Lifetime of Machinery, Equipment, and Goods

Through workshops and training, Fab Labs can teach skills in repairing and maintaining equipment, thereby extending their useful life and reducing waste.

Relation to SDGs: This is connected to SDG 9.1, 9.4, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.3, 12.4, 12.5.

3. Promoting Circular Materials and Approaches

Circular Practice: Prioritize Circular Materials and Approaches

Fab Labs can innovate and prototype using sustainable and circular materials, setting examples for broader industrial practices.

Relation to SDGs: This practice promotes SDG 9.1, 9.4, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.3, 12.4, 12.5.

4. Supporting Regenerative and Local Practices

Circular Practice: Mainstream Regenerative Agriculture

Fab Labs can support and innovate in agricultural practices that regenerate rather than deplete resources, fostering sustainable food systems.

Relation to SDGs: Supports SDG 9.4, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.4, 12.5.

Circular Practice: Go Local, Seasonal, and Organic

By promoting the use of local, seasonal, and organic products and materials (including waste), Fab Labs can reduce the environmental footprint of food systems.

Relation to SDGs: Aligns with SDG 9.4, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.4, 12.5.

5. Industrial Symbiosis and Efficiency

Circular Practice: Mainstream Industrial Symbiosis and Efficiency

Fab Labs can facilitate the path towards industrial symbiosis, being demonstrators of how waste or byproducts from one process are used as inputs for another, improving resource efficiency.

Relation to SDGs: This supports SDG 9.1, 9.4, SDG 11.6, 11.b, and SDG 12.3, 12.4, 12.5.

7 First Iberoamerican FabLabs Meeting.

7.1 Introduction

The First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting emerged as a crucial convergence point for various stakeholders involved in promoting the circular economy in the Ibero-American region. In a global context where sustainability and innovation are imperative, this event serves as a platform for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and collective action. Under the theme "circular community," the meeting brought together FabLabs from across Ibero-America to highlight initiatives and projects that drive the circular economy and explore how these labs can transition towards more circular production models. Led by FabLab CIEC and FabLab UDLA, the event was held in a hybrid format, combining in-person and virtual activities to ensure inclusive participation.

Event Details

Dates: November 23, 24, and 25, 2023

Lucía Lucas, Pieter van der Hijden, Fabricio Santos, Renato Ávila: The State of Circularity in the Ibero-American Countries and the Role of FabLabs and Makerspaces. Exploring Circular Innovation: Insights from the First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting

Description: This distributed event, under the "circular community" theme, featured various online and in-person activities at FabLabs, primarily hosted at Fab Lab UDLA (Quito) and FabLab CIEC (Madrid). Activities took place across Spain and Latin America.

Objective: The main objective was to bring together Ibero-American FabLabs to showcase community initiatives related to the circular economy and generate knowledge on this topic.

Main Work Areas:

Education (.EDU)

Production/Industry (.COM)

Biodiversity (.BIO)

Format: Online, in-person, and distributed activities, depending on each event.

Main Venues: FabLab UDLA (Quito) and FabLab CIEC (Madrid)

7.2 First Iberoamerican FabLabs Meeting – Results Report: Impact

Impact Forecast:

418 FabLabs, 15.43% of the total FabLabs, 5100 users, of which it is estimated that 10% could participate in the event (about 500 people).

Final Impact:

Total attendance	3216
Percentage women	36,10%
Percentage men	63,90%
Degree of satisfaction of those attending the activities	Alto
Number of participating FabLabs	44
Number of participating countries	12

7.3 Conclusions about First Iberoamerican FabLabs Meeting

With the participation of 44 FabLabs, 28 institutions, 50 startups and companies, 12 countries, and 3,216 attendees, the First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting far exceeded the expected levels of participation. This demonstrates the global and multidisciplinary commitment from the Ibero-American region to the circular economy and highlights the capability of FabLabs to bring together key societal actors, ranging from startups and companies to citizens, researchers, makers, and more, including public and private institutions (municipalities, universities, entrepreneurship centers, research centers, etc.).

The democratically chosen theme "circular community" by the FabLabs involved in the organization underscores the philosophy of collaborative work, the importance of shared knowledge, and the need to drive innovation and collective action towards more sustainable and equitable economic models.

Regarding the main work areas of the event, special emphasis was placed on education, production/industry, and biodiversity. This reflects an integrated approach addressing various aspects of the circular economy, from awareness and education to practical implementation in production and biodiversity conservation.

On gender inclusion, there is a notable disparity with 36.1% women and 63.9% men participating.

Finally, it is important to highlight that the future initiatives proposed within the framework of this meeting involve the creation of long-term collaborative networks. This demonstrates, on one hand, the long-term commitment of the Ibero-American FabLabs network to the transformation towards a more circular economic model, and on the other hand, the importance of working together, both locally and globally, to achieve this goal.

8 Conclusions

Fab Labs could play a critical role in advancing circular practices by promoting sustainable consumption, extending product lifespans, using circular materials, and supporting regenerative agriculture and local practices.

On the one hand, the findings of this paper suggest that Fab Labs have:

1. Limited SDG integration:

Only 27.4% of Fab Labs have incorporated SDG profiles into their operations. This highlights a significant gap in leveraging Fab Labs for sustainable development.

2. Underutilized potential for CE:

The low percentage of Fab Labs with SDG profiles indicates a substantial untapped potential. Fab Labs could play a more significant role in achieving global sustainability goals by integrating circular economy principles more widely.

On the other hand, our analysis shows that Fab Labs:

1. Have potential for circular practices:

Fab Labs are uniquely positioned to foster circular practices through various initiatives that align with SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). These include promoting resource efficiency, extending product lifespans, using circular materials, and supporting regenerative agriculture and local production.

2. Are effective platforms for circular practices:

Fab Labs can drive significant advancements in sustainable practices. By focusing on education, industry, and biodiversity, they can promote responsible consumption, extend the life of products, and foster innovation in sustainable materials and methods.

3. Establish collaborative networks:

The creation of networks such as IberoFABLaT is vital for the long-term success of circular practices in Ibero-American region. These networks enable knowledge sharing, collaborative projects, and collective action towards sustainability, amplifying the impact of individual Fab Labs.

4. Have a considerable impact when the work together.

Achievements of Ibero-American Fab Labs Meeting:

The first Ibero-American Fab Labs Meeting, under the theme "Comunidad Circular," demonstrated the collaborative potential of Fab Labs. With participation from 44 Fab Labs, 28 institutions, 50 startups, and over 3200 attendees from 12 countries, the event underscored the commitment to circular economy practices and the role of Fab Labs as hubs for innovation and sustainability.

The convergence of Fab Labs, SDGs, and CE principles represents a powerful opportunity to drive sustainable development. By enhancing their integration of SDGs and promoting circular practices, Fab Labs can play a pivotal role in addressing global sustainability challenges, fostering innovation, and creating a more equitable and sustainable future. The insights and momentum generated from the Ibero-American Fab Labs Meeting provide a robust foundation for expanding these efforts and achieving greater impact across the region and beyond.

9 Recommendations for the future

1. Enhance Awareness and Training:

Increase awareness and training on SDGs among Fab Lab participants to foster a deeper understanding of how their activities can contribute to sustainability.

2. Develop and Implement SDG Profiles:

Encourage more Fab Labs to develop and implement SDG profiles. This could involve integrating specific SDGs into their project planning and operational frameworks.

3. Promote Circular Economy Projects:

Actively promote and support projects that focus on circular economy practices. This includes resource efficiency, product lifecycle extension, and the use of sustainable materials.

4. Foster Collaborations:

Strengthen collaborations with local governments, educational institutions, and industry partners to create a supportive ecosystem for implementing and scaling circular practices.

5. Monitor and Evaluate Impact:

Implement systems to monitor and evaluate the impact of Fab Lab initiatives on SDG targets. Use this data to continuously improve practices and demonstrate the value of these contributions to stakeholders.

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ANNEX 1 – Tables 1-4

Table 1. Levels and trends of SDGs in the Ibero-American region.

Level	SDG 1 - No Poverty
Challenges remain	8
Data not available	1
Major challenges remain	1
SDG achievement	2
Significant challenges remain	10
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 1 - No Poverty
Data not available	1
Decreasing	2
Moderately increasing	4
On track	5
Stagnating	10
Total general	22

Level	SDG 2 - Zero hunger
Major challenges remain	15
Significant challenges remain	7
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 2 - Zero hunger
Decreasing	2
Moderately increasing	4
Stagnating	16
Total general	22

Level	SDG 3 - Good health and well being
Challenges remain	3
Major challenges remain	9
Significant challenges remain	10
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 3 - Good health and well being
Moderately increasing	14
Stagnating	8
Total general	22

Level	SDG 4 - Quality education
Challenges remain	6
Major challenges remain	2
SDG achievement	2
Significant challenges remain	12
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 4 - Quality education
Data not available	1
Decreasing	2
Moderately increasing	7
On track	1
Stagnating	11
Total general	22

Level	SDG 5 - Gender Equality
Challenges remain	10
SDG achievement	2
Significant challenges remain	10
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 5 - Gender Equality
Moderately increasing	14
On track	4
Stagnating	4
Total general	22

Level	SDG 6 - Clean Water and sanitation
Challenges remain	4
Major challenges remain	6
Significant challenges remain	12
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 6 - Clean Water and sanitation
Moderately increasing	15
On track	4
Stagnating	3
Total general	22

Level	SDG 7 - affordable and clean energy
Challenges remain	9
Major challenges remain	1
SDG achievement	3
Significant challenges remain	9
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 7 - affordable and clean energy
Moderately increasing	16
On track	3
Stagnating	3
Total general	22

Level	SDG 8 - Decent work and economic grow
Challenges remain	5
Major challenges remain	6
Significant challenges remain	11
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 8 - Decent work and economic grow
Decreasing	3
Moderately increasing	9
Stagnating	10
Total general	22

Level	SDG 9 - Industry, innovation and infrastructure
Challenges remain	1
Major challenges remain	10
Significant challenges remain	11
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 9 - Industry, innovation and infrastructure
Moderately increasing	13
On track	1
Stagnating	8
Total general	22

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Table 1. Continued. Levels and trends of SDGs in the Ibero-American region.

Level	SDG 10 - Reduced inequalities
Data not available	1
Major challenges remain	16
Significant challenges remain	5
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 10 - Reduced inequalities
Data not available	4
Decreasing	4
Moderately increasing	4
On track	1
Stagnating	9
Total general	22

Level	SDG 11 - Sustainable cities and communities
Challenges remain	5
Major challenges remain	8
Significant challenges remain	9
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 11 - Sustainable cities and communities
Decreasing	2
Moderately increasing	9
On track	1
Stagnating	10
Total general	22

Level	SDG 12 - Responsible consumption and production
Challenges remain	8
Major challenges remain	6
SDG achievement	1
Significant challenges remain	7
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 12 - Responsible consumption and production
Moderately increasing	10
On track	1
Stagnating	11
Total general	22

Level	SDG 13 - Climate action
Challenges remain	12
Major challenges remain	5
SDG achievement	3
Significant challenges remain	2
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 13 - Climate action
Decreasing	1
Moderately increasing	6
On track	7
Stagnating	8
Total general	22

Level	SDG 14 - Life below water
Data not available	2
Major challenges remain	14
Significant challenges remain	6
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 14 - Life below water Level
Data not available	2
Decreasing	1
Moderately increasing	4
Stagnating	15
Total general	22

Level	SDG 15- Life on land
Major challenges remain	17
Significant challenges remain	5
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 15- Life on land
Moderately increasing	3
Stagnating	19
Total general	22

Level	SDG 16 - Peace, justice and strong institutions
Data not available	1
Major challenges remain	17
Significant challenges remain	4
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 16 - Peace, justice and strong institutions
Data not available	1
Decreasing	4
Stagnating	17
Total general	22

Level	SDG 17 - Partnerships for the goals
Challenges remain	5
Major challenges remain	3
SDG achievement	1
Significant challenges remain	13
Total general	22

Trend	SDG 17 - Partnerships for the goals
Moderately increasing	11
On track	6
Stagnating	5
Total general	22

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Table 2. Specific SDG targets related directly with sustainability. Result of textual analysis by authors of United Nations (2015)

<p>4-Quality education</p>	<p>4.7 By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development.</p>
<p>9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure</p>	<p>9.1 Develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and transborder infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all. 9.2 Promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and, by 2030, significantly raise industry's share of employment and gross domestic product, in line with national circumstances, and double its share in least developed countries. 9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities. 9.A Facilitate sustainable and resilient infrastructure development in developing countries through enhanced financial, technological and technical support to African countries, least developed countries, landlocked developing countries and small island developing States.</p>
<p>11-Sustainable cities and communities</p>	<p>11.2 By 2030, provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport, with special attention to the needs of those in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities and older persons. 11.3 By 2030, enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement planning and management in all countries.</p>
<p>12-Responsible consumption and production</p>	<p>12.1 Implement the 10-year framework of programmes on sustainable consumption and production, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries. 12.6 Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle. 12.8 By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature. 12.A Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production. 12.B Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable development impacts for sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products.</p>
<p>14-Life below water</p>	<p>14.2 By 2020, sustainably manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems to avoid significant adverse impacts, including by strengthening their resilience, and take action for their restoration in order to achieve healthy and productive oceans 14.7 By 2030, increase the economic benefits to Small Island developing States and least developed countries from the sustainable use of marine resources, including through sustainable management of fisheries, aquaculture and tourism 14.C Enhance the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources by implementing international law as reflected in UNCLOS, which provides the legal framework for the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources, as recalled in paragraph 158 of The Future We Want</p>
<p>15- Life on land</p>	<p>15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements 15.2 By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally 15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development 15.8 Mobilize significant resources from all sources and at all levels to finance sustainable forest management and provide adequate incentives to developing countries to advance such management, including for conservation and reforestation.</p>
<p>17-Partnerships for the goals</p>	<p>17.4 Assist developing countries in attaining long-term debt sustainability through coordinated policies aimed at fostering debt financing, debt relief and debt restructuring, as appropriate, and address the external debt of highly indebted poor countries to reduce debt distress. 17.15 Respect each country's policy space and leadership to establish and implement policies for poverty eradication and sustainable development. 17.16 Enhance the global partnership for sustainable development, complemented by multi-stakeholder partnerships that mobilize and share knowledge, expertise, technology and financial resources, to support the achievement of the sustainable development goals in all countries, in particular developing countries.</p>

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Table 3. Fab Lab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies (%)

SDGs ranking	Countries	FabLab SDG Profiles: SDG frequencies (%)																
		1 - No Poverty	2 Zero hunger	3 Good health and well being	4 Quality education	5 Gender Equality	6 Clean water and sanitation	7 Affordable and clean energy	8 Decent work and economic growth	9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure	10 Reduced inequalities	11 Sustainable cities and communities	12 Responsible consumption and production	13 Climate action	14 Life below water	15 Life on land	16 Peace, justice and strong institutions	17 Partnerships for the goals
1	Spain	3	3	7	88	55	0	14	18	48	18	55	48	11	0	0	0	14
2	Portugal	0	9	9	81	36	0	27	18	36	0	63	45	18	9	9	0	18
3	Chile	0	0	0	60	0	20	20	0	100	0	100	40	0	0	20	0	40
4	Uruguay	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	Puerto Rico	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	Argentina	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Brazil	0	0	40	80	20	20	20	40	40	0	40	0	0	0	40	0	0
8	Republica Dominicana	0	0	11	75	44	3	3	40	70	9	33	37	3	3	1	0	16
9	Costa Rica	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Honduras	0	33	0	66	100	0	0	66	33	33	0	0	0	0	33	0	33
11	Peru	0	0	0	100	0	0	100	0	100	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	Colombia	16	0	16	83	16	0	8	50	58	25	16	25	8	0	8	0	8
13	Ecuador	0	0	25	100	25	0	0	25	75	25	50	25	25	0	0	0	0
14	Mexico	0	0	0	100	100	0	0	100	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
15	Panama	16	0	5	55	16	11	22	72	77	16	22	5	16	0	0	5	22
16	El Salvador	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	100	100	0	0	0	0	0
17	Paraguay	0	0	0	100	100	0	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
18	Nicaragua	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19	Guatemala	0	0	0	66	0	0	33	33	100	0	33	100	0	0	0	0	33
20	Bolivia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21	Venezuela	0	0	0	100	100	0	0	100	100	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	Cuba	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Average	2,33	3,00	7,53	83,60	40,80	3,60	25,13	30,80	69,13	8,40	47,47	35,00	5,40	0,80	7,40	0,33	18,93

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Table 4. Relation between Ellen Mc Arthur Foundation definition of CE and SDGs targets.

ITEM	FREQUENCY	1 - No Poverty	2-Zero hunger	3-Good health and well being	4-Quality education	5-Gender Equality	6-Clean water and sanitation	7-affordable and clean energy	8-Decent work and economic growth	9-Industry, innovation and infrastructure	10-Reduced inequalities	11-Sustainable cities and communities	12-Responsible consumption and production	13-Climate action	14-Life below water	15-Life on land	16-Peace, justice and strong institutions	17-Partnerships for the goals
biodiversity	6														14.a	15.0,15.4,15.5,15.9,15.a		
climate	9	1.5	2.4									11.b	13.0,13.1,13.2,13.3,13.a,13.b					
consumption	5								8.4				12.0,12.1,12.a,12.c					
ecosystem*	9		2.4				6.6	7.0,7.1,7.2,7.3,7.5,7.b						14.2	15.0,15.4,15.6,15.9,15.a			
energy	6								8.4,8.8	9.4,9.b		11.6,11.a,11.c	12.4,12.c					
environment	11	1.5			4.a													17.7
materials	2																	
pollution	3			3.9			6.3								14.1			
production	6		2.4				6.3		8.4				12.0,12.1,12.3,12.1		14.1			
recycling	3						6.3,6.a						12.5					
renewable	2						7.2,7.a											
resilient	6		2.4							9.0,9.1,9.a		11.0,11.c	12.5					
reuse	3						6.3,6.a						12.5					
waste	7						6.3,6.a					11.6	12.3,12.4,12.5,12.c					
regen	0																	

Circular Economy Definition
 The circular economy is a system where materials never become waste and nature is regenerated. In a circular economy, products and materials are kept in circulation through processes like maintenance, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, recycling, and composting. The circular economy tackles climate change and other global challenges, like biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution, by decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources.
 - It reuses and recycles
 - It reduces and restores
 - It regenerates nature
 Undetermined by a transition to renewable energy and materials, the circular economy is a resilient system that is good for business, people, and the environment.
 Source: Ellen McArthur Foundation
<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy/introduction/overview>

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ANNEX 2 – SDGs levels and trends in Ibero – American region

Derived from accompanying data (Sachs, J. et al. 2024)

Country	SDG 1 - No Poverty	SDG 2 - Zero Hunger	SDG 3 - Good Health and Well-being	SDG 4 - Quality Education	SDG 5 - Gender Equality	SDG 6 - Clean Water and Sanitation	SDG 7 - Affordable and Clean Energy	SDG 8 - Decent Work and Economic Growth	SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	SDG 10 - Reduced Inequalities	SDG 11 - Sustainable Cities and Communities	SDG 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production	SDG 13 - Climate Action	SDG 14 - Life Below Water	SDG 15 - Life on Land	SDG 16 - Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	SDG 17 - Partnerships for Goal Achievement
Spain	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Portugal	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Chile	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Uruguay	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Paraguay	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Argentina	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Brazil	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Republica Dominicana	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Costa Rica	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Honduras	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Puerto Rico	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Colombia	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Ecuador	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Nicaragua	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Panama	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
El Salvador	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Peru	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Mexico	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Venezuela	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track
Cuba	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track	On track

Lucía Lucas, Pieter van der Hijden, Fabricio Santos, Renato Ávila: The State of Circularity in the Ibero-American Countries and the Role of FabLabs and Makerspaces. Exploring Circular Innovation: Insights from the First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting

ANNEX 3 – First Ibero-American FabLabs Meeting Report

Link to the report: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1NRbTZtpMRY7TN7WWjaMog7NDDc0-rOa/view?usp=sharing>